

NFDI4Biodiversity Service Provider Policy

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NFDI4Biodiversity Service Provider Policy

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Introduction

The NFDI4Biodiversity consortium acts as a community-owned infrastructure hub for the national biodiversity community by providing services for research data management, processing and publishing for scientists and further stakeholders in the field. These services are managed in the internal Service Portfolio and made available to the public as a Service Catalog.

The NFDI4Biodiversity Service Provider Policy provides the framework of standards, guidelines, and responsibilities for service providers within the consortium. It aims to ensure that all offered applications and tools adhere to the highest possible levels of accessibility, interoperability, reusability, sustainability and transparency while promoting the principles of Open Science. This service policy is designed to align with the **FAIR**¹ (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles which ensure research data and tools are managed to maximise their value for the scientific community. Additionally, it is (very) welcomed if services also align with the **TRUST**² (Transparency, Responsibility, User focus, Sustainability, and Technology), and **CARE**³ (Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, and Ethics) principles.

The consortium aims to provide services that meet the community needs over the complete research (data) life cycle. Potentially identified gaps will be filled regularly by further services. All services are delivered collaboratively to ensure maximum benefit for the community.

Scope

This policy applies to all service providers within the NFDI4Biodiversity consortium who are offering IT-based services⁴. For service providers offering non IT-based services, such as training, separate policies apply. Service providers are co-applicants or participants offering services which is defined by the NFDI as “a technical-organisational solution, which typically includes storage and computing services, software, processes, and workflows, as well as the necessary personnel support for different service desks”.⁵

The scope of this policy encompasses all software tools, workflows, databases, web applications, libraries/ APIs, and associated documentation developed, maintained, and integrated under the NFDI4Biodiversity initiative - in short the policy applies to all stages of the software and service

¹ <https://force11.org/info/the-fair-data-principles/> (visited latest on 31.01.2025)

² https://en.wikisource.org/wiki/The_TRUST_Principles_for_Digital_Repositories (visited latest on 31.01.2025)

³ <https://www.gida-global.org/care> (visited latest on 31.01.2025)

⁴ The policy follows the NFDI use of this term which encompasses tools and services.

⁵ Quelle: K. des V. N. F. (NFDI) e.V., „Stellungnahme der NFDI-Konsortien zu Basisdiensten“, Feb. 2022, doi: 10.5281/zenodo.6091657.

lifecycle. All services must adhere to the standards and objectives of the overarching goals of the consortium.⁶

Specifically, this includes:

- Newly developed tools and services: All services developed directly within the work programme of the NFDI4Biodiversity consortium. They are called Consortium Services⁷.
- Existing services from partners: services that partner organisations contribute in-kind to the NFDI4Biodiversity community-owned Service Portfolio. They are called Partner Services. If those services are developed further with funds from NFDI4Biodiversity they will be treated as Consortium Services in terms of requirements.

Roles and responsibilities with guiding principles for the selection process

The NFDI4Biodiversity consortium has defined roles and responsibilities to structure and distribute tasks between stakeholders to ensure the functional operation of each single service and the Service Portfolio and Catalog in general:

- **Service Provider:** Service providers are partners which open their own existing infrastructures and tools along the data life-cycle for the community or develop community solutions within the work programme of NFDI4Biodiversity. They are responsible for the FAIR-supporting development, deployment, maintenance (e.g. updates, bug fixes and availability), sustainability and documentation of the software tools and services.
- **Developer:** A person located within the organisational structure of a respective service provider institution. It is his/her task to develop or adapt tools/services which meet the defined requirements.
- **Service Oversight Team:** It ensures the development and consolidation of the Service Portfolio and Service Catalog. It provides oversight and guidance to service providers cooperating with NFDI4Biodiversity along the service life cycle. This team is responsible for the quality monitoring of the Service Catalog and updating the requirements and policies as necessary to reflect changes in community standards, technologies, and legal requirements.
- **Service Coordinator:** He/She leads the Service Oversight Team which is responsible for the overall management of the Service Portfolio and Service Catalog
- **Service Steward:** Is tasked with overseeing the compliance of the services they manage with the consortial and user requirements. They communicate and coordinate with developers and / or the partner organisations to ensure that the services are documented, accessible, and usable. Furthermore they should act as a “hub” for service outreach, training activities etc. Service Stewards are designated by the Service Provider.

⁶ <https://nfdi4biodiversity.org/en/mission-statement/>

⁷ Infrastructure services for the RDC (Platform Services), which are developed within the NFDI4Biodiversity consortium, are regarded as Consortium Services in the context of this policy.

- **Helpdesk Contact:** Provide assistance to users via the NFDI4Biodiversity Helpdesk and handle issues related to the services. They ensure that support is available and that users have access to adequate documentation and support resources. The Helpdesk Contact is an active part of the Helpdesk Team. Ideally, the Helpdesk Contact is the Service Steward as the helpdesk contact represents the service to the user and collects user feedback.
- **Users:** Expected to use the services in accordance with the terms of use and privacy policies stated by the Service Provider and to provide feedback to help improve the services.

The key responsibility of service providers within the NFDI4Biodiversity consortium is to develop, deploy, maintain, sustain and document the software tools and services they provide to the community. The realisation of tool or service specific training and / or the provision of self learning material is also part of the service providers' responsibilities.

- Compliance with legal requirements:
 - Service providers are responsible for ensuring that their services comply with all relevant legal and ethical requirements (see chapter Legal aspects).
 - Services publicly state the terms of their use. Services adhere to privacy regulations. Service providers outline clearly if data that is being made available to the service is used for purposes beyond the immediate user request (e.g. for service optimization).
- Compliance with technical requirements:
 - Online provided services are supposed to be accessible with minimal downtime. To assure the permanent availability, hosting containerized services in the Research Data Commons Infrastructure and/or de.NBI cloud infrastructure and re-using established high-availability services within the scientific community is encouraged.
 - Software and services support widely used domain-specific standard formats for input and output in order to make them compatible with other tools. Metadata formats adhere to widely used minimal standards and are the guidelines for any user uploaded data.
 - Services and tools provided by NFDI4Biodiversity partners which deal with metadata and relevant file formats support at least one of the common standards as a default or recommendation for users.
 - If applicable, persistent identifiers are used within the services' own databases and when referring/linking to external sources also in output of offline tools. The interoperability between offered services that are relevant for each other is highly encouraged whenever possible.
 - Services strive to be accessible by supporting machine-readable formats and support barrier-free accessibility or also by providing access to data or functions through community-relevant APIs (application programming interface)
- Compliance with open access /open source requirements:
 - All types of scientific publications about services created in the context of NFDI4Biodiversity are meant to be published Open Access (e.g. journals, repositories).
 - Software in this context is developed under an [OSI-approved license](#) and the source code is published in openly accessible code repositories and/or archives (e.g. Zenodo), along with appropriate documentation under an open license. This includes

adherence to open licences preferably CC0, CC-BY for data, and MIT or GPLv3 for software, as appropriate.

- Whenever feasible, applications offered in the context of NFDI4Biodiversity are provided free of charge for download in case of offline tools. Similarly, online tools should be provided free of charge with a reasonable quota of usage for scientific uses. Where fees or usage restrictions apply, this is clearly documented in the Service Catalog.
- Implementation of the FAIR Data Principles:
 - Services must support the FAIR Data Principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable). Providers must ensure that their services enable data to be findable, accessible, interoperable with other services and data, and reusable under appropriate conditions.
- Quality Assurance:
 - Service providers must ensure that their services meet the consortium's quality standards, following the roles and responsibilities and taking part in the current established quality management and performance monitoring (see chapter Continuous Service Monitoring and Review).
- Helpdesk Support:
 - Every service provider must designate a Helpdesk Contact. The Helpdesk Contact joins the NFDI4Biodiversity Helpdesk Team to provide information or know-how to ensure users have access to timely and effective assistance.
- Service Portfolio documentation:
 - Service providers must ensure that comprehensive internal documentation for their services is added to the internal Service Portfolio in the form of a Service Profile on the internal project platform. This documentation should provide a detailed overview of the service, including its current state, key features and functionalities, and must be kept up to date.
 - If there is insufficient public documentation available for users, meaning that information about the service is not easily discoverable via search engines, it may be necessary to additionally create user directed article(s) in the public Knowledge Base hosted by NFDI4Biodiversity .
- Training and /or Training material (in compliance with the training policy):
 - The provision of training material and documentation for users is a prerequisite.
 - Training should be either offered online, in presence or could be provided as Self-Learning-Course (training material).
 - If no training or training material is available, it must be developed. The consortium offers support on request. The development process for these resources will be clarified during the onboarding process.
- Outreach:
 - Service providers/ service stewards shall keep regular contact to the Communication Office and provide it with up-to-date service information useful for outreach activities (e.g. overview of features/functions, usage preconditions, usage examples).

Application and Onboarding

The Service Oversight Team will handle service applications and registrations, and proactively reach out to service providers to register their services with NFDI4Biodiversity, ensuring they are available for the benefit of the community users. Furthermore, the Service Provider supports the Service Oversight Team through completing the following tasks during the onboarding process:

1. Clarify Helpdesk Support: Define and document NFDI4Biodiversity Helpdesk support for the service, including contact details and acknowledgement of the current Helpdesk workflows.
2. Add Internal Documentation: Fill in and maintain comprehensive internal documentation in the projects documentation platform (Service Profile)
3. Document Training Activities and / or training material: Provide documentation or links to training activities and available training materials relevant to the service.
4. Provide Summary Slides: Create and submit summary slides that provide an overview of the service, including its purpose, key features, and user instructions.
5. Provide information for NFDI4Biodiversity Service Catalog: Enter the service information into the table, ensuring consistency with the Service Profile and adhering to the word limit for the Service Catalog on the website.
6. Prepare a news article: In cooperation with the Communication Office create a brief news article about the inclusion of the new service in the Service Catalog.
7. Introduction of the Service to the Consortium: The service should be presented to the consortium in at least one of the three formats (BiodiversiTea, Service & Tools Workshops, or Project Forum).
8. RDC article (optional): Create user directed article(s) in the public Knowledge Base hosted by NFDI4Biodiversity.

Continuous Service Monitoring and Review

The monitoring and review was established to support Service providers in improving their services and ensure the quality of their services through appropriate measures based on quantitative and qualitative feedback.

Therefore Service providers are obligated to participate in the continuous service monitoring and review process. This process involves:

- Regular Performance Reviews: Service providers must participate in scheduled performance reviews to assess the quality and effectiveness of their services.
- Feedback and Improvement: Providers are expected to act on feedback received during reviews, including feedback collected by the Service Steward and the Helpdesk Contact as part of the performance evaluation, making necessary improvements to enhance service quality and compliance.

- KPI Monitoring: Service providers must join the KPI monitoring process and provide the required key performance indicators (KPIs) to ensure effective tracking of service performance.
- Reporting: Providers must provide timely and accurate reports as required by the Service Coordinator to support ongoing monitoring and evaluation.

Compliance

Service providers are expected to fully comply with this policy. Non-compliance may result in corrective actions, including exclusion from the NFDI4Biodiversity Service Portfolio or other measures as determined by the Steering Committee. Regular participation in the review process is mandatory and critical for maintaining service integration and quality within the consortium.

Underlying regulations are:

- General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)
- Kodex für gute wissenschaftliche Praxis der DFG
- Kooperations- und Mittelweiterleitungsvertrag